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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17711323>**Evaluation of the Readability, Accuracy, and Comprehensibility of Patient Education Materials Prepared by Nursing Students**Tugce YESILYAPRAK KARACA ^{1*} ¹ Pamukkale University, Denizli Vocational School of Health Services, Denizli² Pamukkale University, Faculty of Health Sciences, DenizliCorresponding Author Email: tyesilyaprak@pau.edu.tr**Article Info**

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Abstract: This study aimed to evaluate the readability, accuracy and comprehensibility of patient education materials prepared by nursing students. This study is descriptive retrospective type. In this study, the readability of patient education materials (n=39) prepared by students studying at a University's Health School Nursing Department and taking the Surgical Nursing course in the spring semester of 2019-2020 academic year in Turkey was examined. Ateşman Readability Test, Flesch–Kincaid Readability Test and Patient Educational Material Checklist were used for evaluation. These materials were related to gastrointestinal, musculoskeletal, urogenital, respiratory, cardiovascular, endocrine system, neurosurgery, breast, eye and burn surgery. Patient education materials prepared by nursing students have poor readability and low intelligibility. Examined in terms of structural layout and content, patient education materials did not meet all the guidelines recommendations regarding structural order and content.

Introduction

Hospitalization, waiting for surgical intervention, the meaning of surgery, lack of education about the surgical procedure, disruption of operations, being away from family, unfamiliar environment and various medical practices are factors that cause anxiety in patients (Fındık and Yıldızeli Topcu, 2012). Patient education materials-PEMs are important for patients who undergo surgery to be informed about the surgical procedure and to make autonomous decisions about the procedures (Morris et al., 2018; O'Sullivan et al., 2020).

PEMs are used in all educational topics related to disease risks, medication use, postoperative exercises, discharge education, home care, social and sexual life (Minutolo et al., 2022). PEMs need to meet certain important criteria to be effective at the terminal level. The European Commission recommends that patient-centered education in PEMs should be readable, understandable and assessable (O'Sullivan et al., 2020; Vooradi et al., 2018).

Readability tests (Flesch Reading Ease and Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level-FKGL) and structural design tests (Baker Able Leaflet Design, Patient Education Materials Assessment Tool-PEMAT) should be used in the preparation of PEMs to meet these criteria (Vooradi et al., 2018) and prepared in line with guide recommendation (Jarernsiripornkul et al., 2019). International literature reports that these materials are not usually prepared according to the recommended criteria, are too long, include medical terms and do not meet patient needs. This condition makes it hard to understand PEMs and decreases the effectiveness of patient education (Ferguson & Pawlak, 2011; Sustersic et al., 2019). Relevant studies examine the readability level of PEMs prepared by medical institutions and healthcare professionals (Boztas et al., 2014; Ferguson and Pawlak, 2011; Sustersic et al., 2019). However, there is no study assessing PEMs prepared by nursing students.

Therefore, the present study sought to assess the readability, accuracy and apprehensibility of patient education materials prepared by nursing students.

Materials and Methods

Research Design

The study was of descriptive retrospective quality.

Setting and Sample

The study sample consisted of all patient education materials (N=62) prepared by students studying in the Department of Nursing at the School of Health of a university in Turkey and taking the Surgical Diseases Nursing course in the spring semester of the 2019-2020 academic year. Twelve of these materials were related to gastrointestinal system, nine to musculoskeletal system, seven to urogenital system, seven to respiratory system, five to cardiovascular system, three to endocrine system, six to neurosurgery, five to ENT, four to breast, three to eye and one to burn surgery. In determining the sample size, the researchers used the known population sampling method ($t=1.96$, $d=0.005$, $p=0.50$, $q=0.50$) and found the sample size to be 39. In sample selection, the researchers used stratified simple random sampling methods. The researchers determined the number of training manuals to be included in the sample from each stratum in line with the number of manuals in the strata. Accordingly, the researchers included eight training manuals on the gastrointestinal system, six on the musculoskeletal system, four on the urogenital system, four on the respiratory system, three on the cardiovascular system, two on the endocrine system, four on neurosurgery, three on ENT, two on breast, two on eye and one on burn surgery.

Data Collection and Tools

The researchers used Ateşman Readability Test and Flesch-Kincaid Readability Test to evaluate the readability of the patient education materials. The researchers evaluated the relevance and structural organization of the materials through a checklist prepared in line with the literature. Two independent researchers examined the content and structural organization of the patient education materials.

Ateşman readability test: This test allowed to assess the readability of texts based on the number of sentences and words using a mathematical formula. The researchers first prepared the test for English texts. Ateşman adapted the test into Turkish in 1997. The Turkish formula of Ateşman Readability Test is as follows:

Readability Level= $198,825-(40,175 \times \text{number of syllables/number of words}) - (2,610 \times \text{number of words/number of sentences})$. Ateşman prepared the test for short texts. Mert (2013) tested the usability of the test in long texts (Table 1).

Flesch–kincaid readability test (FKGL): Readability test was a method testing how easily or how hard the reader understood a text (Boztas et al., 2014) (Table 1).

The formula of the test was,

Readability= $(0.39 \times \text{clause length})+(1.18 \times \text{word length})-15.59$

Word length=Syllable number/word number

Clause length=Word number/clause number (Table 1).

Patient education material checklist: The researchers prepared the checklist in line with the literature. The checklist included information about the suitability of PEMs for the subject and their structural layout. The checklist included parameters related to evidence-based education, surgical risks/benefits, postoperative care, disease content, lifestyle change recommendations, use of photographs and visuals, avoidance of medical terms, indentation and font size. The researchers prepared the checklist with two variables, "yes" and "no". A high number of "yes" indicated that the guidelines were appropriate for the subject and had a high structural regularity.

Data Analysis

The researchers analyzed the study data via the SPSS 25.0 program. They demonstrated descriptive statistics with number and percentage. They assessed readability of the manuals via the Ateşman Readability Test and Flesch–Kincaid Readability Test.

Results

In the study, it was found that PEMs prepared by nursing students consisted of 145.46 ± 67.28 items and 1634.15 ± 733.42 words on average. The mean Flesch-Kincaid readability score of the patient education materials was 56.98 ± 6.06 . This score showed that most of the prepared materials were at the 10th to 12th grade level (Table 1). The mean Ateşman Readability score of the PEMs was 66.37 ± 6.80 . This score indicated that the manuals had reading difficulties (Table 2).

Table 1. Atesman Readability Test and Flesch-Kincaid Readability Test

Atesman Readability Score	Degree of reading difficulty	Estimated Reading Grade Level
90-100	Very easy	-
79-89	Easy	-
50-69	Fairly difficult	-
30-49	Difficult	-
1-29	Very difficult	-
Flesch- Kincaid Readability Score	Very easy	5th grade
90-100	Easy	6th grade
80-90	Fairly easy	7th grade
70-80	Plain	8th and 9th grade
60-70	Fairly difficult	10th to 12th grade
50-60	Difficult	College
30-50	Very difficult	College graduate

Table 2. Readability score distribution of patient education materials

Variables		X±SD	Min-Max	Median
Number of Sentences	Number of	145.46±67.28	35.00-	132.00
	Words		290.00	
Flesch Reading Ease Score	Number of Words	1634.15±733.42	459.00-	1577.00
			3259.00	
Atesman Readability Test	Flesch Reading Ease Score	56.98±6.06	43.70-	58.10
			76.60	
	Atesman Readability Test	66.37±6.80	55.40-	64.70
			81.10	

Readability test. According to this test, 59.0% of manuals had a reading difficulty of very difficult and 15.4% had a reading difficulty. The researchers evaluated the suitability of the patient education materials for the subject with the Flesch-Kincaid Readability test. According to this test, 59.0% of the guidelines were prepared for grades 10 to 12, 20.5% for grades 8 and 9, and 17.9% for high school level (Table 3).

Table 3. Reading difficulty degree and approximate education level according to the reading ease scores of the patient educational materials

Variables		n	%
Atesman Readability Test	Very easy	1	2.6
	Easy	9	23.1
	Fairly easy	23	59.0
	Difficult	6	15.4
Flesch Reading Grade Level	5th grade	1	2.6
	8th and 9th grade	8	20.5
	10th to 12th grade	23	59.0
	College	7	17.9

In this study, the structural order as well as the readability of PEMs were examined, and content analysis was performed. When the structural characteristics of the educational materials included in the study were examined, it was seen that the subject content followed a logical sequence, was supported by simple visuals/photographs, was written in an appropriate font and had spaces for patients to take notes. Although 43.6% of the PEMs were prepared in a short format according to the topic, most of them (82.1%) used medical terms (Table 4).

Among the patient education materials, 74.4% included evidence-based practices, 89.7% explained the purpose of education, 87.2% addressed the disease process in a cause-effect relationship, and 59.0% were prepared in line with patient needs. However, only 2.6% of the guidelines include information on drugs (Table 4).

Table 4. Structural order and content analysis of patient education materials

	Yes		No		
	n	%	n	%	
Structural Order	Supporting patient interaction with questions	6	15.4	33	84.6
	Short format	17	43.6	22	56.4
	Followed a logical order	39	100.0	0.0	0.0
	Supported by simple images/photos	39	100.0	0.0	0.0
	Used medical terms	7	17.9	32	82.1
	Written with an appropriate font	39	100.0	0.0	0.0
	Had spaces for patients to take notes	39	100.0	0.0	0.0
Content Analysis	Including evidence-based applications	29	74.4	10	25.6
	Explaining the purpose of education	35	89.7	4	10.3
	Discussing the disease process within a cause-and-effect relation	34	87.2	5	12.8
	Information related to medications	1	2.6	38	97.4
	Including information about when to apply to the hospital	15	38.5	24	61.5
	Explaining life change after illness	33	84.6	6	14.4
	Preparing in line with patient needs/standard education	32	59.0	16	41.0
Appropriateness of the subject content to the patient's culture	25	64.1	14	35.9	

Discussion

Traditionally, patient education is mostly conducted in a planned and verbal manner. However, the low effectiveness of verbal education necessitated the development of PEMs (Monsivais and Reynolds, 2003). PEMs are easily accessible materials that contain a lot of information such as the disease process, medications used and life changes. If the printed materials presented to patients are concise, patients will adapt to the disease process more easily. Therefore, for the effectiveness of patient education, PEMs should consist of printed material and be readable (Sand-Jecklin, 2007).

Readability is related to the comprehensibility of a text by the reader. As the number of words and sentences in a text increases, the readability level will decrease. According to Atesman, texts longer than three syllables and 30 sentences have a difficult level of readability. Another study reported that PEMs created for physical therapy patients had a higher number of words and clauses (Eker et al., 2013). In this study, the average number of sentences in patient education materials was found to be difficult (Atesman, 1997; Eker et al., 2013), and this is

consistent with the literature. These findings showed that the printed materials presented to patients were prepared in a long format.

The readability of patient education materials is related to the number of words as well as the level of education. It is recommended to prepare patient education materials for grades 6 to 8 (Eker et al., 2013) However, when the literature is examined, it is seen that PEMs are prepared above the educational level of the patients. In a study, it was reported that patient education materials are generally prepared at university level or for grades 10 to 12 and their readability is difficult (O'Sullivan et al., 2020). A study conducted by Singh examining PEMs prepared for cancer patients found that readability level was at 9th to 12th grade (Singh, 2003). A study conducted by Ammanuel et al. (Ammanuel et al., 2020) assessing PEMs prepared online for neuro-oncology patients reported that the materials had a hard level of readability (above the educational level of patients). A study conducted by Wilson (Wilson, 2009) reported that PEMs were very difficult readability for an adult. In national studies, the readability level of PEMs varied from fairly to very difficult, which agreed with the international literature (Boztas et al., 2014; Eker et al., 2013; Keçeci et al., 2019). The present study found that PEMs were prepared for grade 10-12, which was also in agreement with the national and international literature. This may indicate that PEMs in the present study had a hard level of readability.

According to the Turkish Statistical Institute data (Türkiye İstatistik Kurumu, 2020), 18% of Turkey's population has an education level between 10th and 12th grade. According to the United Nations Development Program, the average duration of education for adults in Turkey is 6.5 years. This statistical data may indicate that the educational materials included in the sample of the current study are more suitable for adults with higher levels of education. The difficult readability level of the PEMs in this study (inappropriate for the educational level of the patients) may be related to the nursing curriculum.

Nursing education in Turkey is focused on disease and care. The content related to the development of patient education materials is limited (Keçeci et al., 2019). There is no different course on the preparation of patient education materials in the nursing curriculum. Information on the preparation of educational materials is given in a limited way in the teaching in nursing course. Therefore, students' knowledge in this field remains limited. This may indicate that students cannot fully limit the conceptual framework when preparing PEM.

The readability of patient education materials is related to word-sentence count and educational level, as well as structural order and content. The structural order of printed materials includes the font size of the guide, supporting it with visuals, and avoiding the use of medical terms. Content is the preparation of printed materials in line with patient needs and culture (Keçeci et al., 2019; Monsivais and Reynolds, 2003). In PEMs with difficult readability, there are problems with both structural layout and content. In a study conducted by Ammanuel and colleagues (Ammanuel et al., 2020), it was found that PEMs were not prepared according to geographical region and cultural structure and had a difficult readability level. Singh found that the format length, target audience, and writing style of the PEPs did not meet the criteria and were very difficult to read (Singh, 2003). In another study by Adkins and Singh, it was reported that patient education materials did not meet all the structural appropriateness standards and had difficulty in terms of readability (Adkins et al., 2001). Sand-Jeklin reported that PEMs contain a high proportion of medical terms and that removing medical terms increases the readability of the guidelines (Sand-Jecklin, 2007). Other similar studies have reported deficiencies in the use of medical terms and adaptability to the target audience. Other similar studies have reported deficiencies in the use of medical terms and adaptability to the target audience (Cotugna et al., 2005; D'Alessandro et al., 2001). When the structural order of the PEMs in this study was examined, it was observed that the rate of supporting patient interaction with questions was low; they were prepared in a long format and frequently used medical terms. In terms of content, most of them were not prepared in line with patient needs.

The findings of this study are consistent with national and international literature (Adkins et al., 2001; D'Alessandro et al., 2001; Keçeci et al., 2019; Monsivais and Reynolds, 2003; Singh, 2003).

Different guidelines have been developed to make patient education materials understandable and applicable. Baker Able Leaflet Design, Patient Education Materials Assessment Tool-PEMAT are some of the most frequently used structural layout and content guidelines. Preparation of patient education materials in line with these guidelines can increase the comprehensibility and applicability of printed materials.

Considering that nursing students are a part of the health system, the fact that the printed materials prepared by nursing students were examined in this study constitutes the strength of the study. It is possible to say that the findings of the study reveal the importance of course contents related to material preparation in nursing education. In addition, increasing the awareness of nursing students on the subject may enable them to provide more effective nursing education to their patients, strengthen nurse-patient communication and increase positive patient outcomes in their professional lives.

In line with these results, the researchers recommended that general education and health literacy level of the target audience be determined prior to preparing PEMs. Also, PEMs should be prepared in line with guide recommendations at an understandable level for individuals. PEMs previously prepared by nursing students should be reviewed in line with guides. Teaching in nursing course contents in the nursing curriculum should be reviewed and reorganized. A separate course on PEM preparation should be included in the nursing curriculum. Responsibility will be given to nursing students to prepare education to PEM preparation. Readable PEMs are important for improved quality of life and reduced complications and hospitalizations.

The present study has more than one limitation. One of them was that the general education and health literacy of the patient group to whom education materials prepared were presented remained unknown. Another limitation was that the students who prepared PEMs had not received special training in this area.

Conclusion

According to the results of the present study, PEMs prepared by nursing students had a hard level of readability and a low level of apprehensibility. Examining in terms of structural order and content, PEMs did not meet all guide recommendations related to structural order and content. In line with these results, the researchers recommended that general education and health literacy level of the target audience be determined prior to preparing PEMs. Also, PEMs are prepared in line with guide recommendations at an understandable level for individuals. PEMs previously prepared by nursing students are reviewed in line with guides. Course contents of teaching in nursing included in nursing curriculum be reviewed and rearranged. A separate course related to PEM preparation is included in nursing curriculum. Responsibility will be given to nursing students to prepare education for PEM preparation. Readability PEMs are important to increased life quality, decreased complication and hospitalization.

The content evaluation of the patient education materials in the sample included the readability, relevance to the topic and structural organization of the guidelines. Written permission was obtained from Pamukkale University Non-Interventional Clinical Research Ethics Committee (60116787-020-161712) before the study

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